

Post Colonial Issues and Women in Asif Currimbhoy's Plays

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Abstract

Asif Currimbhoy is the notable Bengali writer. He goes back to Socio-political condition in the society with a view to making them a vehicle of another vision. The paper attempts to examine the plays of Asif Currimbhoy from a women's perspective. Theme, portrayal, picture and psychology of the women have been focused with the reason to assess Asif Currimbhoy's vision, concern, attitude and treatment of the female issue. His profound pull humanism and worry for the upliftment of Indian women have delivered two sets of characters one the traditional representing the gendered subalternity.

Keywords: Feminism, suffering, modernity, tradition, desire.

Asif Currimbhoy as "a man of the theatre" because his plays hold theatric significance and his plays are actable unlike his predecessors plays which are rarely or seldom actable due to the importance given to lyrical and allegoric forms. He chose the themes from the real life incidents that hold social, historical and religious importance. The reason behind his selection of the unusual themes is the socio-literary condition in which he grew. He gets to know the culture of various people due to his visit to various places because of the nature of his job and it helped him in depicting realistic characters. He wrote about twenty nine plays and Asif Currimbhoy is purely a playwright and he did not contribute to any other literary forms. In his plays women characters significant role. M. K. Naik writes: "As a playwright he has no equal: ever since he began writing in the late fifties, he has averaged almost two plays a year" (262). Till his death on 1st June 1995, he had produced twenty nine plays of all shades of thought. Naik is of the opinion that 'sheer quantity' in the absence of the 'quality of vision' cannot make him a great dramatist.

The Miracle Seed, The Hungry Ones and The Dumb Dancer are the three selected plays written by Asif Currimbhoy that are taken for study. The readers can see that the women characters do not seem to have much significant role to play in his dramas. But still, in almost all his plays, though women have minor roles to play, it has its own many layers of interpretations which are symbolic and

one can see the skill of the playwright in the art of characterization. Meserves comments thus: “In Asif’s best plays the power of his women characters dominate the action... in retrospect one finds Asif Currimbhoy’s women character, whether minor or major, stronger and more memorable than his men”. (XXI)

Malti in *The Miracle Seed*, Razia in *The Hungry Ones*, Prema and Sakuntala in *The Dumb Dancer* are some of the remarkable women characters portrayed by Asif Currimbhoy in his plays. Malti in *The Miracle Seed* is portrayed as a responsible family woman, who stands by the side of her husband at the crucial time of famine as a moral support. Malti is portrayed as a full-fledged woman which means that she plays the role of a daughter-in-law, wife and mother. Malti is presented as a clever as well as wise character and she has never failed to update herself about the steps taken by the government to help the suffering people. In *The Miracle Seed*, when Ram gives importance to his pregnant wife Malti. Malti becomes so happy to hear her husband words: “I like to see you smile. It is careworn ... and sweet” (10). Malti is also pious and she worships the Lord Ganesha regularly for the well being of her family by garlanding the God. When Ram spits on the idol of the God, in the mood of desperation due to famine, Malti becomes so much worried for her husband’s indifferent behavior towards God and asks for his forgiveness to Ram or to punish her for her husband’s mistake. Indian women always have the heart and sacrificing mind to bear even the sins committed by their beloved and Malti is an example for that attitude. While the treatment of women is one side, the femine is a post colonial issue to be discussed. Due to the absence of canals and dams in the villages, there is famine over there. Due to the irresponsible and indifferent and biased attitude of the government people suffer in famine. Moreover the above mentioned attitude is inherited from ex colonizers British government in India.

Razia is a Muslim woman who stands as a tribute to the Indian culture and she is the symbol of virginity which is the part and parcel of the Indian culture. Razia is a typical Indian woman character through whom the playwright symbolically represents the holy culture of “One man for one woman”. Razia makes her escape good when Al, an American tries to rape her to take revenge on Ramesh who is her lover. Razia also strictly follows her religious norms that are engraved in the holy Quran like offering food to the beggars and the suffering lots with motherly love and care during the month of Ramzan.

In *The Hungry Ones*, the post colonial issue to be discussed is the Hindu- Muslim Unity. The British gave freedom to India with an agreement to divide India into India and Pakistan which resulted in the discrimination between the Hindus and Muslims. It has also further resulted in the frequent communal riots that affected the lives of many innocents and women.

Prema and Sakuntala in *The Dumb Dancer* show a different dimension of women characters. Prema is depicted as an evil woman who has gone to the extent of killing Sakuntala to keep Bhima as a lover for herself. As a coin has two sides as head and tail, women also have two extreme nature. One is to do anything under the sun to keep their beloved always at peace and with happiness. Sakuntala falls under this type. Another is going to any extreme level of evil to spoil the enemy’s life or to kill someone or to spoil something that serves as an obstacle to obtain their loved favourite things or a person (may be lover).

Asif Currimbhoy’s women are presented as strong, powerful and energetic in *The Miracle Seed* and woman as an ideal, faithful wife and loving and caring mother in providing food to the needy and the hungry people in *The Hungry Ones*. Asif Currimbhoy has not failed to project right on the dangerous character of woman going ever to any extent of killing another woman to keep the latters’ man for herself. He portrays the violent nature of women as well as the sacrificing nature of women for their beloved in *The Dumb Dancer* through the character of Prema and Sakuntala.

Prema in *The Dumb Dancer* is a psychiatrist who treats Bhima. Sakuntala is his lady love. Prema starts to develop a sort of liking towards Bhima because of his love for Draupadi in a lunatic state. Prema goes to the extent of murdering Sakuntala in order to keep Bhima for herself and she persuades Sakuntala to come in the guise of Duryodhana telling that she strives hard to cure Bhima by creating a real life situation in which he will kill Duryodhana who insulted Draupadi. Here the readers can see that the women are powerful and their power can be used for creative as well as destructive purposes like this.

Thus in this study of the women in the dramas of post-independent dramatist, no strict pattern is followed. Sometimes, the play of the playwright is compared. In short, one can say that the drama of Asif Currimbhoy, can be called as the mirrors of the society that reflect the status, and position of the women in the contemporary period.

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